

Management of communicative space of students in the higher education system

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Abstract. At the present stage of social development, the education system is undergoing a global transformation due to the increasing complexity of requirements for competitive professionals. The essence and peculiarities of communicative space of student youth are revealed in the article. The communicative space includes the communicative roles, the communicative sphere, the communicative situation and the communicative settings.

Education plays an important role in the context of international integration, world globalization and transformation. This is due to the rapid socio-economic changes in society, resulting in the formation of new educational parameters in higher education, which require transformation and change in the educational process. The urgency of the problem is that the development of higher education must be linked to the requirements of the state, the prospects of the country, the interests of society [1]. In this regard, there is a need to transform the educational space in the context of society's demands on young professionals. Society of the new generation expects a high level of professionalism, which should stimulate the higher education system to prepare a competitive specialist who has a high level of professional and communicative competence.

Changes in the education system create new demands on social roles and, accordingly, on teachers' activities. The role of the teacher in the new educational environment can be defined as facilitating the student's self-determination and self-realization through improving the interaction between students and teachers.

There are accepted samples of students' and teachers' life and activities, as well as the peculiarities of their communication at each HEI. The accepted models in this case are general understanding of the culture of behavior, rules of activity and learning, the system of role positions of students and teachers, the interaction between them. They give an opportunity to talk about the educational scenario adopted in society. The educational scenario is a sequence of actions of the participants of the educational process to achieve the goal in the training of young specialists [2]. The storyline is taught at HEI by writing requirements for interaction, communication between students and teachers.

The notion "communicative space" [3] naturally follows from the notion "communication" [4], which in this context is understood as the process of establishing and maintaining contacts between members of a social group created on the basis of spiritual, ideological or other unity of members of society. Communication space is a system of social and professional, business and interpersonal communications [3]. Communication features depend on the social roles and social status of the communicants, the content of the communication acts and the results of the interaction [4].

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The students' communicative space has external and internal forms. The internal form of the communicative space consists of the features of interaction within the framework of HEI: communication student-student, student-group, student-teacher, teacher-teacher, student-administration, teacher-administration. The external form of communication takes place outside HEI: it is the communication of students and teachers with other higher education institutions, communication of teachers in the professional community, students with future employers, HEI and graduates.

The communication process between a teacher and a student is the interpenetration of three realities: information, psychological and cultural one. The realities of teacher and student in ritual communication only collide, forming a narrow channel of a single communication space. In business communication, a teacher and a student obtain a common reality: an informational and communicative space that has a temporary existence. A constant single psychological reality is formed in the transition to the personal level [5]. It is defined by the business purpose of communication, common interests, interest in each other, and time frames of communication are given by the chronotype of the educational process, the degree of personal closeness, desire of the subjects [3, 5].

Therefore, the authors propose to create conditions in HEI under which students and teachers will be able to choose each other to improve the overall communication space and improve the quality of training of young specialists.

Involving students in teaching environment through taking into account their perspective on higher education life, emphasizing the importance of their thoughts. These all form a new level of responsibility that is necessary in shaping the competence of graduates. In addition, it contributes to the organization of a common communication environment, resulting in a collective thinking and perception of HEI as a reference group. The purpose of this study is to analyze the communicative space of students, to study its peculiarities in the process of transformation of educational scenarios in HEI. In order to achieve this goal, it is necessary to solve the following tasks: 1) to analyze the peculiarities of communication of students with the curators of specialization (scientific supervisors) in the educational process; 2) to explore the dynamics of interaction between students and curators of academic groups; 3) identify the dynamics of satisfaction with graduates' learning for future regulation of the educational process.

In order to obtain sufficient information about social reality, the dynamics of changes taking place in the HEI require special collection and processing of information, most fully reflect the changes. Monitoring is an effective way to accomplish this. Monitoring refers to the observation of the learning process in order to identify its relevance to the desired result.

The objectives of any monitoring include: timely forecasting and identification of negative aspects of learning that affect the quality of education; evaluation of the effectiveness of the implemented measures; information support for the management of the educational process.

Sociological monitoring is a system of tracking changes that occur in the HEI based on the study and analysis of mass perceptions of them. Its main task is to obtain new and systematic information, not once, but systematically, in small periods of time.

An analysis of the dynamics of changes that occur in the evaluation of the parameters offered to students gives an opportunity to speak about the level of effectiveness of communication with teachers for the formation of professional competence of graduates. This article examines two criteria of professional competence, namely theoretical and practical training in the HEI and indicators of communicative space, such as interaction of students with curators of specialties and curators of academic groups.

The features of the students' communicative space were studied during 2016-2019 with 425 students of different courses, faculties and HEI in Kharkiv.

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First, we proceeded from the fact that the level of activity of cooperation with the curator in the specialization to some extent reflects the relations between students and their teachers (Table 1).

Table 1

The level of activity of cooperation with the curator of specialization in different years (%)

Level of activity	Years of research			
	2016	2017	2018	2019
Active cooperation	11,42	23,6	32,85	43,95
Cooperation is not full	47,52	37,93	39,9	36,53
Lack of cooperation	41,06	38,47	27,16	20,52

Survey data indicate that the majority of students surveyed in 2016 (47.52%) did not cooperate fully with their curators, did not communicate with them at all (41.06%) and actively interacted with their curators by specialty the smallest number of students (11.42%).

Compared to this data in 2017, one can see an increase in the level of cooperation with the curator. Thus, the number of such students who actively cooperate with their specialty curators increased to 23.6%, those who did not cooperate fully with the curator decrease to 37.93%. The number of students interviewed who do not interact with their curators has changed slightly.

Survey in 2018 indicates that a significant number of students (39.9%) were collaborating with their curators but not in full, actively interacting with them already 32.85%, and not cooperating at all - 27.16%.

Finally, in 2019, a significant number of students cooperate with their curators in full 43.95%, do not cooperate fully with their specialty curators 36.53%, do not cooperate at all - 20.52%.

As the number of persons actively cooperating with the curators has increased significantly from year to year, and the number of students who do not cooperate with their curators by specialization has significantly decreased, we can say that there is a clear positive dynamic in such relations.

Topical in our study is also the issue of interaction between students and curators of academic groups that perform mainly educational function in interaction with students. The data is presented in table 2.

Table 2

Levels of interaction with curators of academic groups in different years (%)

Level of activity	Years of research			
	2016	2017	2018	2019
Active cooperation	68,33	70,33	80,99	88,73
Lack of cooperation	31,67	29,67	19,01	11,27

A positive dynamic in respondents' relationships with teachers in an educational context is demonstrated in table 2. The activity of curators in 2019 increased by 20.5%

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compared to 2016. A teacher and a student is in a multifaceted relationship. Their interaction involves not only the transfer of knowledge, control over learning, but also taking into account the individual characteristics of students. A teacher should be an example for a student youth in everyday life, and therefore he needs to be up-to-date in dealing with problematic situations. A young specialist is made competent by his environment, which is taken as referent one, he inherits theoretical, practical and evaluative attitudes.

The authors also studied the dynamics of student satisfaction with theoretical and practical training. The assessment was performed on a 5-point scale. The survey includes graduates of various HEI of 2016-2019.

The dynamics of theoretical training assessment are presented in Table 3.

Table 3

Level satisfaction in points	Years of research			
	2016	2017	2018	2019
1	-	-	0,21	1,3
2	-	2,0	2,01	1,4
3	9,09	8,19	10,96	10,57
4	43,99	45,18	47,49	45,46
5	46,92	48,63	39,27	41,28

Assessment of theoretical background as a whole showed that it was at a fairly high level. Thus, in 2016, 46.92% of students evaluated theoretical education as excellent, 43.99% as good. Thus, 90.91% of the respondents rated their theoretical background in HEI quite high.

In 2017, the theoretical background was assessed by graduates as follows: maximum satisfied (five points) - 48.63%, four - 45.18%. In 2018, the theoretical background was assessed by graduates as follows: five points - 39.27%, four - 47.49%, overall figures indicate a positive assessment of theoretical background at 86.76%.

In 2019, it was rated five points by 41.28% of students, four points by 45.46% of students.

Attention is paid to the positive dynamics of the assessment of theoretical training until 2017. Since 2018, the overall level of satisfaction with theoretical training has decreased, probably due to the fact that the number of hours spent on theoretical work has been reduced.

the assessment of the practical training has shown that it was at an average level. The dynamics of practical training assessment are presented in Table 4.

Table 4

Years of research	Level of satisfaction in points				
	1 point	2 points	3 points	4 points	5 points
2016	3,16	12,48	32,01	39,53	11,64
2017	3,19	11,33	32,33	44,41	13,02
2018	5,99	14,83	33,52	35,08	10,59
2019	8,1	15,11	29,82	33,77	12,68

Practical training was estimated by the graduates of 2016 as follows: four points - 39.53%, three points - 32.01%, and maximum satisfied, five points are only 11.62% of students. In 2017, a rating of four was 44.41%, 32.33% for practical training and 13.02%

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for five. Practical training is assessed by the graduates of 2018 as follows: 35.08% of students rated it as four points, 33.52% have chosen three points, 14.84% have marked two points. In 2019, the dominant rating was four points - 33.77%, three points were rated by 29.82% of students, five points marked 12.68% of students.

The ratings of "three", "four" and "two" remained virtually unchanged. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the process of study at the HEI in order to obtain higher results in assessing satisfaction with the practical training of graduates.

Studies show that the satisfaction with theoretical training of graduates is significantly higher than the satisfaction with practical training.

The monitoring results provide valuable information to identify strengths and weaknesses in the organization of the educational process, to correct the activities of HEI and to improve the quality of training.

Information according to the results of the monitoring is needed to manage the graduate training process. Management we do understand as deliberate impact on people and objects that is carried out to obtain the desired results. The desired result implies the formation of a productive communicative space of students, which will facilitate the training of a specialist with a high level of professional competence.

The communication space is managed in several stages. In the first stage, prognostic management is carried out aimed at identifying the most suitable transformations in the higher education system. This stage of management is aimed at determining the possible trajectories of students' communication space development, making a forecast in case of productive introduction of innovations. At this stage, it is decided that the purely theoretical material should go into the past. Interactive and dual learning systems meet the new goals and needs of education as a whole. Active forms of education not only form the knowledge, skills and skills, but also the personal characteristics of students, which are necessary for success in a professional community. In addition, it is necessary to improve the communication quality of students with specialty curators and academic group curators. This helps to improve the quality of knowledge among students.

The next stage of management takes place throughout the training. This is an evaluation management, the essence of which is monitoring. This monitoring aims to evaluate the dynamics of students' perception of innovations in the communicative space. For several years, it has been monitored how far the ideas adopted during the prognostic phase of management are being implemented.

At the last stage there is management that can be called training. Its essence is to increase the professionalism of teachers, to expand additional classes for students. Management consists of correction of the activity of a teacher, organization of the learning process, determining the vectors of professional development of teachers and students. The transformation of the student's knowledge control system is to minimize the tasks aimed at reproducing material, the successful reproduction of which is possible by notching up lecture notes and tutorials. Questions of creative nature will give an opportunity to check the quality of the competences formed.

The implementation of the process of managing the communicative space of students is based on the fulfillment of a number of principles: planning, coordination, stabilization, accordance.

The principle of planning. According to this principle, every higher education institution has its own grounded plan of activity and development. Planning is related to the formulation of the mission and goals of the HEI : strategic, tactical and operational ones. Each of them involves a number of small tasks, the solution of which will bring HEI closer to fulfill a global mission.

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The principle of coordination. Each institution needs to monitor strategic, tactical and operational changes and make appropriate adjustments in accordance with available resources. This principle is that for any specialist there are limits to the amount of information processed. If this limit is exceeded, the efficiency of coordination of resources and their proportions will decrease.

The principle of stabilization. Each subsequent innovation should be introduced after the previous one has stabilized. It is necessary for new resources to be superimposed on the stable previous ones.

The principle of accordance. Planned changes should be appropriate for each other in terms of technical, intellectual, rational and other characteristics.

The priority of higher education at the present stage of society development is to create optimal conditions for students to acquire a system of professionally important competences, so any form of training providing mastery of practical skills become especially relevant.

There are a number of new trends in higher education today:

- restructuring of higher education;
- the prestige of some HEI, specialties, professional knowledge increases sharply and at the same time the prestige of others falls;
- career dependence on education is on the rise; education is today a necessary but not the only condition for a successful career.

The effectiveness of transformations of the educational space is studied by establishing feedback with consumers of educational services (with students). As active participants in the learning process, students and graduates report their satisfaction with the special competencies they have formed.

As a conclusion, it should be noted that the implementation of the above mentioned innovations will shape the HEI scientific and educational process orientation to the formation of high level of practical skills of students necessary for effective practical performance.

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